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Cite as: AIP Advances 15, 035014 (2025); doi: 10.1063/9.0000914

Submitted: 11 November 2024 • Accepted: 3 January 2025 •

Published Online: 10 March 2025

View Online

Export Citation

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Note: This paper was presented at the 16th Joint MMM-Intermag Conference.

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ABSTRACT

We observed that the annealing of Co-rich microwire at variable temperature allows to develop graded magnetic anisotropy. In such microwires, annealed with a temperature gradient, gradual variation of the hysteresis loops along the microwire length is observed. While inclined hysteresis loops are observed in as-prepared Co-rich microwires, perfectly rectangular hysteresis loops are obtained for microwires annealed at high enough temperature. Accordingly, single-domain wall propagation is observed in Co-rich microwires segments with rectangular hysteresis loops. In microwire segments annealed at intermediate temperatures, irregular hysteresis loops are observed. The origin of such hysteresis loops discussed considering magnetization rotation and DW propagation contributions. We observed that in Co-rich microwire with graded magnetic anisotropy the domain wall velocity is not uniform.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Amorphous magnetic materials have attracted particular attention in applied and basic research due to their unusual combination of extremely soft magnetic properties and excellent mechanical properties and relatively simple and fast fabrication technology.^{1–7} The greatest technological interest is focused in amorphous ribbons or wires.^{1–13} In latter may exhibit spontaneous magnetic bistability^{6,8,9} and/or Giant Magneto-Impedance, GMI, effect.^{10–12} While it should be noted that both the GMI effect and induced magnetic bistability can also be observed in amorphous ribbons,^{13,14} the highest GMI effect and spontaneous magnetic bistability are

reported in amorphous wires.^{8,9,15} Accordingly, magnetic properties of amorphous wires are intensively studied during last 3 decades.^{8–12}

Recently special attention is paid to studies of glass-coated amorphous microwires, which not only have reduced dimensionality, but also covered by insulating and biocompatible glass-coating.^{9,10,15–18} In fact, the Taylor-Ulitovsky preparation technique is suitable for the manufacturing of glass-coated microwires with the widest range of metallic nucleus diameters (between 0.2 and 100 μm).^{14,15} The combination of magnetic softness, high GMI effect and magnetic bistability with superior anti-corrosion and mechanical properties of glass-coated microwires has stimulated several emerging applications in smart composites with embedded

microwire sensitive to external stimuli (magnetic field, applied stress or temperature) for health monitoring, magnetoelastic sensors or biomedical applications.^{19–24}

The preparation method, involving rapid solidification of a metallic nucleus surrounded by an insulating glass-coating with rather different thermal expansion coefficients, is a source of magnetoelastic anisotropy owing to predominantly axially directed internal stresses.^{25–27} Therefore, stresses relaxation allows effective tuning of magnetic anisotropy of glass-coated microwires.^{16,28} Thus, stress-annealing allows inducing transverse magnetic anisotropy in both Fe- and Co-rich glass-coated microwires, while even furnace annealing substantially affects magnetic properties of Co-rich glass-coated microwires.^{16,28,29} In both cases, the annealing temperature, T_{ann} , and time, t_{ann} , are the effective parameters affecting the hysteresis loops of the annealed glass-coated microwires.^{16,28,29} Accordingly, we recently proposed to use stress-annealing in temperature gradient to develop graded magnetic anisotropy in Fe-rich glass-coated microwires.^{30,31}

Previously, it was reported preparation of thin films with graded magnetic anisotropy using quite complex techniques, such as changing the chemical composition during the thin films deposition.^{32,33} The principal interest in such materials with a continuous magnetic anisotropy gradient is related to effective control of the domain wall, DW, nucleation and propagation.³⁴

As mentioned above, hysteresis loops of Co-rich glass-coated microwires can be effectively modified by annealing or stress-annealing. Thus, annealing allows to obtain Co-rich glass-coated microwires with perfectly rectangular hysteresis loops in which single domain wall propagation is observed. Therefore, it is expected that annealing of Co-rich glass-coated microwires in temperature gradient can be suitable for design of graded magnetic anisotropy in Co-rich microwires.

Accordingly, in this work we present our recent results on preparation of Co-rich amorphous microwires with a graded magnetic anisotropy and magnetic properties of such microwires with graded magnetic anisotropy.

II. EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

We studied effect of annealing in temperature gradient on hysteresis loops and DW propagation in Co-rich $\text{Co}_{69.2}\text{Fe}_{3.6}\text{Ni}_1\text{B}_{12.5}\text{Si}_{11}\text{Mo}_{1.5}\text{C}_{1.2}$ (metallic nucleus diameter $d = 22.8 \mu\text{m}$, total diameter $D = 23.2 \mu\text{m}$) glass-coated microwire with vanishing and negative magnetostriction coefficient, λ_s , (-0.3×10^{-6}).²³ Studied microwire has been prepared using Taylor-Ulitovsky technique, consisting in melting of the metallic ingot previously placed inside the glass (Duran) tube, drawing the glass capillary from the softened glass. After filling this capillary with the molten alloys the glass-coated microwire is drawn, quenched by the water jet and finally winding onto a rotating bobbin.^{16,25} Generally this technique allows preparation quite long (up to a few km long) continuous microwires covered with the insulating glass coating in a few minutes.^{16,25}

We studied 30 cm long $\text{Co}_{69.2}\text{Fe}_{3.6}\text{Ni}_1\text{B}_{12.5}\text{Si}_{11}\text{Mo}_{1.5}\text{C}_{1.2}$ microwire sample, which was annealed in a conventional furnace (Thermolyne 62700) with temperature gradient (see Fig. 1). A temperature profile exists in any real furnace, as discussed elsewhere.^{35,36} The temperature profile in the used furnace was determined by measuring the temperature using the commercial (NiCr-Ni)

FIG. 1. Scheme of the annealing in temperature gradient and temperature distribution inside the furnace when the furnace temperature was set to 300 °C.

thermocouple, moving it along the position of microwire. As shown in Fig. 1, in the central part of the furnace there is a zone with a constant temperature, T . However, closer to the furnace walls there is a temperature gradient (see Fig. 1). Accordingly, part of the annealed sample in the zone close to the furnace wall was annealed in the T - gradient, while part of the sample placed in the central furnace zone was annealed at constant T . Given the presence of an insulating glass coating, the studied microwires were annealed in air.

The hysteresis loops of the studied microwires were measured using the fluxmetric method, previously developed and successfully used to measure the hysteresis loops of soft magnetic microwires.³⁶ This method was originally developed for measuring a long (10 cm) sample placed in a thin (about 8 mm of diameter) and long (120 mm) solenoid producing a homogeneous magnetic field, H . A short (2 mm long) movable pick-up coil was used to measure local hysteresis loops in different parts of the microwires, as described

FIG. 2. Hysteresis loops of as-prepared sample (a) and the same sample annealed at 200 °C (b) 300 °C (c).

FIG. 3. Hysteresis loops of studied microwires annealed in variable T_{ann} -gradient measured using short pick-up coil at $T_{ann} = 20^\circ\text{C}$ (a), $T_{ann} = 150^\circ\text{C}$ (b), $T_{ann} = 250^\circ\text{C}$ (c) and $T_{ann} = 300^\circ\text{C}$ (d) and the scheme of the graded magnetic anisotropy appearing as a continuous magnetic anisotropy gradient over the microwire length after annealing in T_{ann} gradient (e).

in our previous publications.^{30,31} The hysteresis loops of studied microwires we represented by as normalized magnetization M/M_0 versus H (where M is the magnetic moment at a given H and M_0 is the magnetic moment of the sample at the maximum H -value).

The DW velocity, v , was evaluated using the Sixtus-Tonks-like experimental technique, previously used for studies of single DW propagation in magnetic microwires.^{9,30,31} Briefly, employed experimental setup consists of three pick-up coils separated by the

same distance, l , surrounding studied microwire and placed coaxially inside a long solenoid producing uniform magnetic field.^{9,30,31} One end of the studied sample is placed outside the magnetizing solenoid to ensure the DW propagation from the opposite microwire end.^{9,30,31}

Accordingly, v -values can be evaluated measuring the time difference, Δt , in the peaks of electromotive force, EMF , induced by the propagating DW in the pick-up coils, from

$$v = \frac{l}{\Delta t} \quad (1)$$

The amorphous state of studied sample has been confirmed by a broad halo in the X-ray spectra obtained using X-ray diffraction.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The hysteresis loop of as-prepared and annealed at constant annealing temperatures, T_{ann} , 200 °C and 300 °C samples are shown in Fig. 2. From Fig. 2 it is evident, that hysteresis loops are remarkably affected by annealing, particularly by T_{ann} . Similar dependence of magnetic properties of Co-rich glass-coated microwires with low negative λ_s -values on annealing was previously observed in various Co-rich microwires.^{16,29}

As expected from experimental results provided in Fig. 2, substantially different local hysteresis loops (measured by movable short pick-up coil) are obtained in the sample, annealed at variable T_{ann} (see Fig. 3). A gradual modification of the hysteresis loops from almost linear (typical for as-prepared sample) to perfectly rectangular along the microwire length is obtained in the microwire annealed with a temperature gradient (see Fig. 3). This transformation correlates with the change in T_{ann} . The schematic representation of the microwire with graded magnetic anisotropy is shown in Fig. 3(e).

The most unusual hysteresis loop is observed at $T_{ann} = 150$ °C (see Fig. 3(b)), at which irregular hysteresis loop is observed. This hysteresis loop shape can be attributed to the contribution of both magnetization rotation (as in as-prepared sample with a linear hysteresis loop) and magnetization switching due to DW propagation (as in an annealed sample with annealing induced magnetic bistability). Finally, at $T_{ann} \geq 250$ °C the hysteresis loops becomes almost perfectly rectangular (see Figs. 3(c) and 3(d)). Accordingly, sample annealed in T_{ann} gradient present spatial variation in local hysteresis loops.

The origin of graded magnetic anisotropy observed in Fig. 3 must be attributed the change in domain structure along the sample length. In terms of core-shell model of domain structure of magnetic wires with rectangular hysteresis loop the radius of the inner axially magnetized core, R_c , can be evaluated from the remanent magnetization, M_r/M_0 as

$$R_c = R(M_r/M_0)^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

being R is the microwire radius.

Accordingly, we can assume that graded magnetic anisotropy in microwire annealed in T_{ann} gradient is related to gradual change in domain structure, reflected in a gradual change in the radius of the inner axially magnetized core.

As mentioned above, it was predicted that the graded magnetic anisotropy must affect the DW. As can be observed in Fig. 4,

FIG. 4. $v(H)$ dependencies in microwire annealed at constant T_{ann} (a) and in T_{ann} gradient (b).

the DW propagation in microwire with graded magnetic anisotropy is essentially non-uniform DW: the DW velocities v_{1-2} and v_{2-3} (i.e. measured between pick-up coils 1-2 and 2-3) are substantially different (see Fig. 4(b)). While, for the same microwire annealed at $T_{ann} = \text{const}$ $v_{1-2} \approx v_{2-3}$ (see Fig. 4(a)).

It is worth noting that a faster DW propagation (higher v -values) are observed in the microwire segments with the lower reduced remanence, M_r/M_0 . This difference in the v -values can be related to the effect of the transverse magnetic anisotropy on DW dynamics. An improvement in v -values was attributed to the influence of the transverse magnetic anisotropy in a similar way as the transverse magnetic field.^{37,38}

Resuming obtained experimental results, we showed that annealing of Co-rich microwires with a temperature gradient can be useful for preparation of microwires with graded magnetic anisotropy and controlling the DW dynamics. Annealing with a temperature gradient is rather simple tool that can be used to large amount of samples without the use of controlled electrodeposition.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

We observed graded magnetic anisotropy in Co-rich microwire annealed in temperature gradient. In such microwires, a gradual variation of the hysteresis loops along the microwire length is obtained. While inclined hysteresis loops are observed in as-prepared Co-rich microwires and annealed at low temperature, perfectly rectangular hysteresis loops are obtained for microwires annealed at high enough temperature. At intermediate annealing temperature irregular hysteresis loop attributed to the contribution of magnetization rotation and DW propagation are observed. A single domain wall is observed in segments of Co-rich microwires with rectangular hysteresis loops. We observed that the domain wall propagation is essentially non-uniform and hence can be effectively controlled. Accordingly, annealing in a temperature gradient

allows to design graded magnetic anisotropy in Co-rich magnetic microwires. Obtained Co-rich microwires with graded magnetic anisotropy are potentially suitable for the development of the position sensors and for in magnetic logic devices using a single DW propagation.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was supported by EU under “INFINITE” (HORIZON-CL5-2021-D5-01-06) project and “Harmony” (HORIZON-CL4-2023-RESILIENCE-01) projects, by the Spanish MICIN, under PID2022-141373NB-I00 project, by the Government of the Basque Country under Elkartek (MOSINCO and ATLANTIS) projects and under the scheme of “Ayuda a Grupos Consolidados” (ref. IT1670-22). The authors thank the technical and human support provided by SGIker of UPV/EHU (Medidas Magneticas Gipuzkoa) and European funding (ERDF and ESF).

AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

Author Contributions

P. Corte-León: Data curation (equal); Formal analysis (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Validation (equal); Visualization (equal). **V. Zhukova:** Data curation (equal); Formal analysis (equal); Funding acquisition (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Project administration (equal); Validation (equal); Visualization (equal). **J. M. Blanco:** Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Validation (equal); Visualization (equal). **J. Gonzalez:** Funding acquisition (equal); Investigation (equal); Project administration (equal). **A. Zhukov:** Conceptualization (equal); Formal analysis (equal); Funding acquisition (equal); Investigation (equal); Project administration (equal); Resources (equal); Supervision (equal); Validation (equal); Writing – original draft (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal).

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding authors upon reasonable request.

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